

THE METHOD OF DEVELOPMENT OF PERCEPTIVE ABILITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS AIMED AT INCREASING THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS.

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Abstract: Forming the knowledge, skills, and abilities of students in terms of creative thinking in a traditional educational environment based on a mechanism aimed at developing social activity based on a methodical approach, creating a foundation for students to acquire the necessary knowledge by improving the methods of developing their social activity, developing students' social activity to achieve creative activity in the educational process by establishing active creative cooperation between the student and the teacher, as a result, mental skills are formed in the minds of students, and their social activity is developed, which is spiritually mature, physically healthy and intellectually developing the personality formation system has been improved.

Key words: Activity, social activity, young generation, educational methods, methods, technologies, non-traditional methods.

Today, the main goal of developing the social activity of students is to make the young generation mature in all respects, perfect people necessary for the development of our society. A perfect person embodies spiritual and physical maturity. In order to develop the social activity of students, folklore, folk tales, stories, legends, children's encyclopedias, and children's books reflecting visual expression play a key role. In addition, the heritage of Eastern thinkers, poems and ghazals, works of art serve as a program. Socio-political, philosophical and educational work of several world-famous thinkers such as Ahmed Yassavi, Bahauddin Naqshbandi, Al-Bukhari, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn-Sina, Muhammad al-Khorazmi, Abul Qasim Firdaws, Amur Temur, Alisher Navoi, Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur. if work is done based on their views, the work of developing students' social activity will become more perfect.

When studying the history of the development of educational methods in Central Asia, it can be seen that various educational methods are used in practice. Among them, Abu Ali ibn Sina in his work "Tadbir al-manazil" says that it is necessary to educate young children in a certain order from birth to adulthood. considers it preferable to teach children in a team rather than individually and writes about the superiority of this method: "Students feel a thirst for knowledge during study and education. When students are together, they talk to each other and thereby develop their imagination and speech.

The problems of educating a creative person had a special place in the researches of Jan Amos Comenius, who emphasized that the human sensory organs, which help to study existence, take the leading place in the cognitive system, empirical, scientific and practical stages in the development of cognitive processes, the main sources of knowledge. described the nature of consciousness and senses.

Forming the knowledge, skills and abilities of students on creative thinking in the traditional educational environment on the basis of a mechanism aimed at developing social activity based on a methodical approach, creating a foundation for students to acquire the necessary knowledge by improving the methods of developing their social activity, developing students' social activity to achieve creative activity in the educational process by establishing active creative cooperation between the student and the teacher, as a result, forming mental skills in the minds of students, forming a morally sound, physically healthy and intellectually developing person with developed social activity system has been improved.

The continuous creative activity of the teacher increases the effectiveness of education. From the elementary school age, students should have a certain idea about their needs. At this time, new aspects of the need are opened, along with meeting these needs, there is also the need to form the personality in a positive way. This process cannot happen without the cooperation of the teacher, of course.

As a result of research, the following competences for the development of social activity of students were determined: on the application of theory to practice:

on the application of methods and technologies to the educational process.

- to be able to choose the method of developing the social activity of students during literacy training through non-traditional methods, picture compositions.

- logical thinking, development of rich imagination, fantasy, creativity, development of professional interests, familiarity and friendship with nature, understanding of national customs and traditions and universal human values, creative application of this knowledge, analysis and generalization of facts , to be able to draw conclusions in this context;

- to understand the content and importance of the lesson, to determine the main methods, methods and means of imagination development, to acquire skills and qualifications.

The analysis and discussion of the results of the teaching experience allows us to draw the following conclusions. The dynamics of imagination, its creative

activity and productivity are directly related to the educational system of students: it is necessary to create favorable external and internal conditions for teachers to reveal their creative potential more effectively.

The stronger the first impression of the thing to be remembered, the more vivid the image associated with it. In addition, the material that is recalled in the stream of information that is relevant and attractive to us is also well remembered.

Every developing junior schoolboy differs depending on himself, his perception of the surrounding reality in one way or another, his perception of the surrounding world, his differentiation of things and events, and his understanding. We hear and distinguish the sounds of birds and musical melodies, we see things, smell different smells, taste different foods and have an idea about it.

In order for the child to become a perfect person, it is necessary to awaken the imagination of studying in him from the elementary school age. It is necessary. In the end, a person is formed in all aspects.

We use some information to solve all sorts of mental problems. However, there are cases where the available information is insufficient for a definitive solution. In this case, the activation of thinking and imagination becomes almost weak.

In conclusion, the function of imagination is very important in the mental development of a child. However, fantasy, like mental activity, should have a positive direction of development. It should help to get to know the world better, to promote self-discovery and self-improvement of the individual, and not to become a passive concept, to replace real life with dreams.

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